

LITERATURE AS A BRANCH OF LINGUISTICS

Ashurova Muhayyo Rustamjon kizi

3rd years student on the faculty of English language and literature
at Fergana State University

E-mail address: Ashurovamuhayyo89@gmail.com

Abstract: This article explores the intersection of literature and linguistics, highlighting the ways in which linguistic analysis enriches the study of literary texts. It discusses how linguistic tools and theories can be applied to analyze various aspects of literature such as narrative structure, characterization, discourse patterns, and stylistic features. The article also examines the role of language in shaping literary meaning and the insights gained by studying the linguistic dimensions of literary works. Through a multidisciplinary approach, it demonstrates how the study of literature within the framework of linguistics offers valuable insights into language use, literary creativity, and cultural significance.

Аннотация: В этой статье исследуется пересечение литературы и лингвистики, освещаются пути, с помощью которых лингвистический анализ обогащает изучение художественных текстов. В ней обсуждается, как лингвистические инструменты и теории могут быть применены для анализа различных аспектов литературы, таких как структура повествования, описание персонажей, модели дискурса и стилистические особенности. В статье также рассматривается роль языка в формировании литературного смысла и выводы, полученные в результате изучения лингвистических аспектов литературных произведений. Благодаря междисциплинарному подходу в статье демонстрируется, как изучение литературы в рамках лингвистики дает ценную информацию об использовании языка, литературном творчестве и культурном значении.

Abstract: ushbu maqola adabiyot va tilshunoslikning kesishishini o'rganib, lingvistik tahlilning badiiy matnlarni o'rganishni boyitish usullarini yoritib beradi. Unda adabiyotning rivoyat tuzilishi, xarakteristikasi, nutq naqshlari va uslubiy xususiyatlari kabi turli jihatlarini tahlil qilish uchun lingvistik vositalar va nazariyalarni qanday qo'llash mumkinligi muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada, shuningdek, adabiy ma'noni shakllantirishda tilning roli va adabiy asarlarning lingvistik o'lchamlarini o'rganish natijasida olingan tushunchalar ko'rib chiqiladi. Multidiscipliner yondashuv orqali u tilshunoslik doirasida adabiyotni o'rganish tildan foydalanish, adabiy ijod va madaniy ahamiyatga oid qimmatli tushunchalarni qanday taqdim etishini namoyish etadi.

Keywords: Text linguistics, literary text, linguistic analysis, literary analysis, language use, communication, linguistic units, syntactic, morphological, lexical, discourse structure, communicative function, linguistic theories, methodologies, historical context, social context, cultural context, linguistic variation, language change, linguistic data, linguistic commentary, linguo-stylistic analysis, text categories, communication, cognition, reality, textual variation, linguistic system, text levels, semantic roles, literary devices, metaphor, irony, discourse analysis, syntactic patterns, lexical patterns, text presentation, language stratification, intertextual connections, literary works.

The issue of investigating and researching a linguistic unit like a text is of special significance nowadays within the framework of actively emerging disciplines of philological and linguistic knowledge. Text is a very significant, multifaceted, and highly complicated idea. Text linguistics, also known as "theory of text," is a special branch of linguistic science with one of its main goals being to view the text as a special linguistic unit, different from other units of a language and speech categories. The problem of its formation and functioning arises at the intersection of linguistics, literary studies, and semiotics. It is important to emphasize several methods for characterizing the text comprehension issue, with regard to literary texts in particular. Literature is closely related to linguistics

because it is a medium through which language is used to convey meaning, emotions, and ideas. Literature is a form of art that involves the use of language to create works of fiction, poetry, drama, and other genres. Linguistics, on the other hand, is the scientific study of language and its structure, including its syntax, morphology, phonology, and semantics. Text is believed to be a multi-faceted unit as a concept, being a particular linguistic unit and the object of investigation of a specific linguistic branch. The idea of text and the category of phenomena, whether linguistic or speech-related, should be connected with are currently not agreed upon by linguists. While some studies focus on the grammatical aspects of text, others see it more as a speech phenomenon that is first and foremost driven by communicative goals. These discrepancies in the examination of the concept of text may be seen in the methodological and linguistic writings of renowned linguists. According to Professor I.R. Galperin, text is a speech product that is written and consists of a name (the headline) and a certain number of language units (called "super-phrasal units") connected by various lexical, grammatical, and stylistic links. Grammatical and semantic completeness are identified as important properties of the text as a specific language unit by the researcher since text is "characterized by completeness, wholeness, and coherence." N. M. Shansky, a native language linguist, defined text as a link of at least two assertions that allows for the completion of the minimal act of communication, such as the exchange of information or thoughts between partners. In addition, V. A. Lukin defines text as a communication that takes the form of a series of signs, has formal coherence, meaningful integrity, and a formal-semantic structure deriving from their interaction. The definitions provided above demonstrate that all academics work to identify the text's position within the linguistic system before allocating the actual text categories that are unique to this linguistic unit. Despite all the distinctions between these definitions, they have a lot of similarities. Text is seen as the byproduct and fundamental unit of speech. As a result, the creation and interpretation of texts take place throughout the communication and cognition of

reality. Text is often expressed through writing, where it has its own internal organization and exhibits the coherence of its constituent elements. According to Y.M. Lotman, the literary text represents a certain view of the world and conveys a message through the language of art.

Several distinct characteristics are implied by the literary text. These include:

1) fiction, convention, and indirectness;

2) synergetic complexity; a literary work is a complex system that uses a national language on the one hand while running its own code and attempting to be understood by the reader on the other;

3) the consistency of text categories created by newly acquired "increments of meaning";

4) the interrelation and interconnection of all text units or the isomorphism of all text levels;

5) the reflexive quality of a poetic word, the revival of words' inner forms, the enhanced actualization of lexical elements;

6) the occurrence of implicit meanings;

7) the impact on the meaning of a literary text and intertextual connections.

In the latter part of the 20th century, text linguistics emerged as a distinct philological field of study. The major goal of text linguistics is to create categories that capture the substance of a text (for instance, its construction principles) and enable the reduction of all textual variation to a small number of readily discernible fundamental kinds. A literary text's linguistics occupy a unique place. It deals with the deliberate interaction of text units, most frequently that which takes place at various text levels. The most common type of text presentation involves layers, and it focuses on language stratification by choosing the right levels of the text at the phonetic, morphological, lexical, and syntactic levels. As a result, it realizes several semantic and aesthetic roles.

In addition to that, linguistic analysis of literary works can provide insights into the historical, social, and cultural context in which they were written, as well as the author's intentions, attitudes, and beliefs.

Literary analysis can also be informed by linguistic theories and methodologies. For example, a linguistic approach to literary analysis might involve examining the use of metaphor, irony, or other literary devices from a linguistic perspective, analyzing the syntactic or lexical patterns of a text, or investigating the discourse structure and communicative function of a literary work. In this way, literature can be seen as a branch of linguistics, as it provides a rich source of data for linguistic analysis and can be studied through linguistic theories and methodologies. Literary works are considered to be important sources of linguistic data, as they reflect the language use and linguistic structures of their time and place of origin. They can also shed light on linguistic variation, language change, and language use in different social and cultural contexts. Hence, The following techniques for linguistic analysis of a literary work are listed by Professor Novikov:

1) linguistic commentary, the primary goal of which is to provide a dictionary or interlinear explanation of illegible, uncommonly used, obsolete, special words and expressions, grammatical phenomena, and other related language facts (the primary subject of the analysis is the text's linguistic level, partially extralinguistic one);

2) linguo-stylistic analysis, which examines figurative language used in a literary work and the aesthetic impact that their synthesis has; the focus here is on finding a synthesizing principle in the ways of speech representation;

3) comprehensive linguistic analysis that aims to conduct a complicated, in-depth philological investigation of a literary work. The primary approach in this research is the definition of the text's figurative poetic structure, which closely relates to the text's content and its system of figurative language meanings. The foundation of a synthesis analysis is the category of the author's image. It is

necessary to explain the ideological purpose of the writing, aspects of its genre, and the aesthetic functions, as well as the poetic (compositional) structure of the text, the system of literary images, and how they are evolving in the narrative. Additionally, linguistic analysis analyzes the functional role of linguistic units and their forms in speech, including the appropriateness of word choice, speech turns, and grammatical forms that are in line with the author's aim and the text's particular use of language. A comprehensive linguistic text analysis model that incorporates information from various linguistic fields, such as theories of speech acts and genres, stylistics, philosophy, and psychology, appears to be urgently needed today. The contemporary linguistic analysis encompasses stylistic analysis, which looks at how each author uses language, as well as literary analysis, which looks at a work as a historical fact of social thinking growth. Since there are no accidental features in the literary text that can be ignored or left without the analysis, every word and every sign in the text delivers information that aids in understanding the nuances of the overall meaning, receiving, and seeing the message.

References:

1. Adolph R. The Rise of Modern Prose Style.- Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1968. — 276p.
2. V.Vositov (2022).Classification theory of Turkic borrowings. “International journal of world languages” Scientific Journal, Tom-1, 11-14
3. G.Ibragimova (2021). Structural and Semantic Properties of Parenthesis in English Essays. “International Journal of Multireligious Understanding.” Scientific Journal, Tom-8, 163-168
4. B.Otajonov, A.Ismoilov (2023) “Nominative field of English and Uzbek means expressing the concept of “Mouth”” Organization Committee-153 p

5. B.Otajonov(2023) “The nominative field of means expressing the concept of “Mouth” in English and Uzbek”. “Journal of Language and linguistics” Scientific Journal, Tom-6, 171-183
6. Q.Umirzaqov (2012) “Ellipsis in complex sentences as a grammatical and semantic phenomenon in different languages” Филология мэсэлэлэри, Баку, Озарбайжон Республикаси, Том-6, 321-323
7. I.Abdullayev(2023) “Characteristics of mutual function of parts of speech in English and Uzbek”, Евразийский журнал академических исследований, Том-3, 7-10
8. G.Zaynobiddinova(2019) “The fifteen stages of teaching number for pupils”, "Science and education in the modern challenges of the xxi century"
9. R.M.Yaqubjonova (2023) ”Language and culture in english classrooms: greetings, ways of expressing politeness” Наука и инновация, Том-1, 66-68
10. Sh. Xamraqulova (2024) “ Unique features of toponymic slangs in English language” SCHOLAR Tom-2, 87-94
11. M.Abduraimova (2022)“The Importance of Teaching English at Early Age in Pre School-Education” Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, Tom-6, 55-60
12. D.Tuxtasinova(2022) “How to teach english language medical engineering specialty students” International Scientific Conference" Innovative Trends In Science, Practice And Education" Tom-1, 157-162
13. N.Boltaboyeva, N.Latipova (2022) “National And Cultural Variety Of Phraseological Unit Of The English Language.” Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka, Tom-2

14. Sh. Umirzaqova (2022) “Using language experience approach in training TFL.” Scientific Ideas Of Young Scientists | Pomysly Naukowe Mlodych Naukowcow Научные Идеи Молодых Ученых Том-6, 76-79